

Politics and family relations in Cristina García's novel "Dreaming in Cuban".

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"For me, the sea was a great comfort, Pilar. But it made my children restless. It exists now so we can call and wave from opposite shores."

~ Cristina García, Dreaming in Cuban

Cristina Garcia's novel *Dreaming in Cuban*, describes Cuba under Fidel Castro's regime, how Communist Ideology influenced the relationships of members of the *Del Pino* family. Another important theme in the novel is the *Cuban exile*, which can be considered as a kind of "escape" from Cuba. We also must consider the fact that "*Garcia's novels suggest that women's dreams, memories, and personal relationships can begin to heal the wounds of the divided nation. Garcia gives voice to three generations of women that lived and suffered the Cuban revolution, and she does so by using unusual discourses that challenge traditional narratives of war.*"¹In this essay, we will show how the Revolution is conceived and how political beliefs divide the members of the Del Pino family into several threads. We will see the impact of the Revolution on the third generation, a generation that in some way determines the future of Cuba. We will also look at how the Revolution is conceived in three generations, and try to make a Revolution/identity comparison in Pilar Puente's case.

The divergence of political views begins in the genesis of this family, in Celia and her husband Jorge. Celia supported the Revolution, but on the other hand, Jorge was against the Revolution. It seems that this discrepancy between the political beliefs of the parents is followed by their children. Thus, together with Celia, his son Javier was also a supporter of the Revolution, but on the other hand, Lourdes (the eldest daughter), like her father Jorge, was completely against the Revolution. Felicia was also opposed to the Revolution, but later she severed ties with the "outside world" and focused more on religious practices (here we must remember that communist ideology was anti-religious).

Garcia, although in disconnection/frequency, has given us a detailed portrayal of the character development of the characters and the reader has a panorama of the life of the individuals of

¹ Ciria, Concepción Bados. "'Dreaming in Cuban', and 'The Agüero Sisters': Re-Writing the Cuban Revolution." *Revista Hispánica Moderna*, vol. 54, no. 2, 2001, pp. 510. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/30207977. Accessed 18 June 2021.

this family. If we do an analysis of Celia's characteristics, we will see a mixed portrayal: both as an individual and as a personification of Cuba. We think that Celia ceased to exist as an individual at the moment when the Revolution appeared in the background. But on the other hand, this can be dismissed because it must be said that it was probably not the Revolution of Fidel Castro that separated Celia from the family, or rather the family from Celia. Celia stayed in Cuba because of a greater love for the Revolution, a love for her homeland, Cuba. This love for Cuba probably made Celia accept both the Revolution and the actuality in Cuba. This Love for Cuba, could also be the reason why Celia kept asking Pilar to stay with her, so that Celia could *inherit* Cuba to Pilar... On one hand, Lourdes and Jorge criticize the Revolution as capitalists and as individualists, but on the other hand Celia practices its humanitarian side. This humanism arises from the love for Cuba that Celia practices through volunteer work. Celia's volunteerism runs counter to the capitalism and/or 'individualism' of Jorge and Lourdes. *This may be one of the reasons for the divergence of political views, because Celia's love for Cuba could be the same as the "love" that the Revolution or El Lider had for Cuba.* So we can say that maybe Celia adored El Lider because the two of them shared the same love for Cuba. Javier supported the Revolution because he saw it as a way of escape from Cuba, or (maybe) from his father...

In Javier's case, we see that the Revolution was not an obstacle to escape from Cuba. Thus Javier, although a supporter of El Lider, again fled Cuba. Thus, we can say that regardless of the political conditions in Cuba, it is **probably** the *Cuban Spirit* itself who seeks to flee Cuba. Javier certainly supported the Revolution and Celia was pleased with that. But Javier could also contribute as a communist to Cuba, but he chose to migrate to Czechoslovakia. Thus, we hypothesize that the *Cuban Spirit* itself is unstable, and that the Revolution further fostered this instability. Thus in the novel we have plenty of instances where the male goes on long journeys around the world working as a salesman or even a naval merchant (Jorge del Pino, Hugo Villaverde).

Ivanito's departure is also very significant because metaphorically Ivanito is the representative of the future, of the Cuban youth. His migration to the USA can be interpreted as a description of the future, of the intention of the younger generations to flee Cuba. If we take a look at the history of Cuban immigration to the US, Canada, Mexico and Europe from 1970 to 2018, we will see that this level of migration has increased every year: *"Historically, Cubans have been among the top ten immigrant groups in the United States since 1970, and in FY 2018 were the seventh largest group, with more than 1.3 million Cubans accounting for*

roughly 3 percent of the overall immigrant population of 44.7 million. The United States is the top destination for Cuban immigrants, followed by Spain (141,400), Italy (37,300), Canada (19,000), Germany (13,400), and Mexico (12,900), according to mid-2019 United Nations Population Division estimates."²

In Lourdes's case, things can be more complicated because her emotional relationship with her mother is 'damaged' since Lourdes was a baby. With the birth of Lourdes, Celia had a mental breakdown because, in one way or another, Lourdes was the reason/obstacle why Celia did not go towards her happiness, towards Gustavo's love in Spain. Celia in a way denies the newborn Lourdes: *"In the final dialogue with her husband, before he took her to the asylum, Celia talked about how the baby had no shadow, how the earth in its hunger had consumed it. She held their child by one leg, handed her to Jorge, and said, "I will not remember her name."*" (Garcia, 42-43)

Lourdes grew up close to her father and was always against Celia's beliefs, and moreover, these differences or discrepancies were highlighted when the Communist Ideology/Revolution appeared in Cuba. Lourdes could not appreciate Celia's blind faith in the Revolution and in El Lider. In her study, Julie Tate emphasizes the view of William Luis who speaks of a **desire** that Lourdes (and her father) has to hurt Celia: *"Lourdes's exclusive attachment to her father allows her at once to distance herself from Celia and to compensate for the absence of a close relationship with her mother. In his study of the novel, critic William Luis states that Lourdes's antagonistic feelings toward her mother are a principal motivation for her alliance with her father. According to Luis, the close relationship between Lourdes and Jorge may be interpreted as the product of "revenge" and "a desire to hurt and defy the mother". This reading reflects Celia's interpretation of Lourdes's relationship with Jorge as well, and it is clear from the text that Celia suffers as a result of Lourdes's rejection."*³

If we make a comparison of the relationship between mother-daughter and son-father, we will see that Lourdes's relationship with Celia is almost the same as Javier's relationship with his father Jorge. Javier never saw his father again and all this father-son emptiness maybe implies a kind of "denial" that Jorge or Javier may have made to each other. Lourdes and Celia also see this kind of gap or severance of emotional relationships between family members. Politics is a cause of the severance of these emotional relationships.

² Blizzard, Brittany, and Jeanne Batalova. "Cuban Immigrants in the United States." *Migrationpolicy.org*, 2 Feb. 2021, www.migrationpolicy.org/article/cuban-immigrants-united-states-2018.

³ Tate, Julie. "Matrilineal and Political Divisions in Cristina Garcia's *Dreaming in Cuban* and *The Agüero Sisters*." *Letras Femeninas*, vol. 32, no. 2, 2016, pp. 149., www.jstor.org/stable/23023039.

In a brief analysis of Lourdes's life in Cuba, we can say that Lourdes could not accept the Revolution for several reasons: First, because *the Revolution raped her*. The second reason is that Lourdes was capitalist in nature and her character showed this. Lourdes is the perfect example of a woman who copes and succeeds in American capitalist life. Cuba did not offer much to Lourdes because Cuba (Revolution) only took from Lorde. When we say "took", we mean the seizure of the property of Lourdes and Rufino, but also rape is a kind of occupation. Lourdes's thoughts, character, ideas were in conflict with Communist Ideology. Thus, for Lourdes, fleeing Cuba was a kind of **freedom** and/or **salvation**: "*Lourdes associates Cuba with pain, suffering, humiliation and inhumanity, with a loveless mother whose allegiance to Castro she cannot comprehend, and with a brutality of her own people [...] the last memory she has of Cuba is a place of chaos and of violence where nothing makes more sense than unintelligible scratches made by the rapists on her skin, signs and symbols of her emotional trauma*"⁴

Felicia's relations with politics are not much mentioned in the novel, but in one moment it is pointed out that she also does not support the Revolution. Felicia represents the 'traditional', past, or old Cuba, and this old tradition is emphasized by the practice of the **Santeria** religion: "*Santeria is a religion native to Cuba. It is a very spiritual-religious way of life[...]Santeria stems from the African religion Yoruba and was forced to come to the New World because of the slave trade.*"⁵ Felicia, as a practitioner of the santeria religion, metaphorically is **a victim to the Revolution**: "*After Castro gained control of Cuba and the implementation of the 1976 Constitution, his administration governed as a Communist regime. He eliminated the practice of all religions, including syncretic religions. He outlawed the open practice of religions, shut down religious sites of worships, and banned religious symbols.*"⁶ Communist ideology destroyed Felicia's mental and spiritual state. "*She's the symbol of old Cuban values, everything that the Revolution set out to destroy because it did not fit the new norms or ideology.*"⁷

⁴ Popescu, Veronica. "Hyphenated Identities in Cristina García's *Dreaming in Cuban* and *The Agüero Sisters*." *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai Philologia*, vol. 62, no. 1, 2017, pp. 160-161., doi:10.24193/subbphil.2017.1.11.

⁵ Kindler, Michelle. "Santeria: Its Growth and Changes as a Result of its Major Relocations." *The Review: A Journal of Undergraduate Student Research* 1, 1997, pp 9. <https://fisherpub.sjfc.edu/ur/vol1/iss1/4>.

⁶ Glaude, Ludmille, "Political Implications on Santería". *Undergraduate Research* 43, 2018, pp.9. <https://digitalcommons.lasalle.edu/undergraduateresearch/43>

⁷ Popescu, Veronica. "Hyphenated Identities in Cristina García's *Dreaming in Cuban* and *The Agüero Sisters*." *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai Philologia*, vol. 62, no. 1, 2017, pp. 162., doi:10.24193/subbphil.2017.1.11.

The Celia-Felicia relationship is like a water-fire relationship.⁸ Metaphorically, Felicia is possessed by a burning sensation (e.g., syphilis is a kind of burning; tendency to set fire to Hugo). On the other hand, Celia is more connected to the sea, the water. Thus, Celia was able to extinguish the fire that burned Felician all those years. In connection with what we said above, we can say that the Revolution in a way created a barrier even in Celia's relationship with Felician. Although not as strong as that one with Lourdes, the barrier that the Revolution created between Celia and Felicia was enough to destroy Felicia spiritually and mentally. This barrier was broken at the time of Felicia's death because Celia agreed to carry out her last wish: to be buried as a santeria (religious practices were forbidden at the time).

So far we have only seen political-family relations between the Del Pino family members. We have noticed that politics has a divisive role in this family because the members of it see politics from different perspectives, and in some way fail to criticize themselves for the political beliefs they defend and believe. It seems that politics transcends family relationships and has a primary role for the individual. For Celia and Javier politics is "salvation" because for e.g in Celia's case, politics can be related to the love for Cuba, to patriotism. In Javier's case, politics is salvation because through the Revolution he manages to realize his dreams and (perhaps) manages to escape his father's pressure/tyranny. For Lourdes and Jorgen the Revolution was also a way of escape because the denial of communist ideology provided them with capitalist-type freedom. The erosive/destructive function of the Revolution is found only in Felicia. Now let us see how politics is conceived in three generations: *Celia-Lourdes-Pilar*.

We mentioned that the Revolution is irreplaceable for Celia and one of the reasons may be the "equal love" that Celia and the Revolution have for socialist Cuba. For Lourdes, we said that the Revolution was a suppressive machine of ideals and dreams; a propaganda cage of lies. As for Pilar, she did not know what the Revolution was until she went to visit Cuba with her mother. Pilar, like Lourdes once, finds no freedom in Cuba. Moreover, this freedom is related to its artistic activity. Her rebellious art is against the Revolution, and in a way Pilar realizes that it's art, her artistic soul does not belong to that country. In fact, Pilar had lived in Cuba only in her imagination and in some moments that connected her to Celia. Thus Pilar had created an imaginative structure for Cuba, a structure which collapsed the moment she saw it with her own eyes.

⁸ Shmoop Editorial Team. "Felicia Del Pino in Dreaming in Cuban." *Shmoop*, Shmoop University, 11 Nov. 2008, www.shmoop.com/study-guides/literature/dreaming-in-cuban/felicia-del-pino.

It seems that Pilar's Cuba had nothing in common with the current Celia Cuba: "*Pilar is the "bicultural character at the crossroads" (Kevane, 97), frustrated by her realization that she has misremembered Cuba and misunderstood her own connection with the island for so long. By identifying Cuba with her own mother, she has simply reduced it to a set of positive features associated with the images of happiness and safety. The reality, however takes her by surprise. Celia represents a Revolutionary Cuba that has become old and obsolete in the 1980s.*"⁹ The trip to Cuba made Pilar understand its cultural identity, its origins. It enabled Pilar to understand which country she belonged to: "*...sooner or later I'd have to return to New York. I know now it's where I belong- not instead of here, but more than here.*" (Garcia, 236) *With these final words Pilar begins a new stage in her identity-formation, incorporating her American and her Cuban identities in a new fashion which is entirely her own.*"¹⁰ Here lies the role of politics or the Revolution in the third generation of this family. The spirit of the future cannot rot in Castroian communist hypocrisy. This bloodthirsty policy was neither for Pilar nor for Ivanito. It is politics that lift the Cuban spirit to leave Cuba, always politics ... Pilar finally found peace because it was precisely the abuela / revolution that enabled her to define her identity, to find her peace.

The way the identity-Revolution relationship is presented in three generations would be represented schematically as follows:

According to the scheme, Celia and Lourdes represent two extremes because their views on the Communist Party were completely different. The question that may arise is why did we place Pilar between these two extremes? A little above we noted that Pilar before going to Cuba had created imaginative thoughts about Cuba, a panorama built from the time Pilar had spent with Celian on the beach. After visiting Cuba, Pilar realized that Cuba was not really what she thought it would be, and her opinion of Cuba began to resonate with that of Lourdes: "*She has to allow her mother's special kind of Cubanidad to be part of her identity, because it represents a side of the hyphen that she must acknowledge, just as her grandmother represents the other side.*"¹¹ It should be noted that Pilar is not like her mother who was not an exile but an "*American-in-the-making, rejecting her homeland, her culture, her Cubanidad,*

⁹ Popescu, Veronica. "Hyphenated Identities in Cristina García's *Dreaming in Cuban* and *The Agüero Sisters*." *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai Philologia*, vol. 62, no. 1, 2017, pp.163., doi:10.24193/subbphilolo.2017.1.11.

¹⁰ Popescu, Veronica. pp.164.

¹¹ Popescu, Veronica. pp.163.

reinventing herself as citizen of this new country."¹² On the other hand, Pilar is not even like her grandmother Celia, because Pilar can not sacrifice the things she wants, just as Celia did. Pilar feels Cuban, loves Cuba and her grandmother, but in one moment, Pilar realizes that Cuba is not her home. Pilar finally feels and accepts the fact that her home is in New York: "*I'm afraid to lose all this, to lose Abuela Celia again. But sooner or later I'd have to return to New York. I know now it's where I belong- not instead of here, but more than here.*" (Garcia, 236)

In conclusion, we can say that the government of Fidel Castro, the Cuban communist ideology, showed dissatisfaction in many families in Cuba. These dissatisfactions also led to inconsistencies in the political beliefs of the Del Pino family. These discrepancies in political beliefs followed a physical and emotional distance that certainly brought only spiritual ruin to this family and especially to Celia, whose tragedy is further emphasized by the "abandonment" of Pilar for the second time. However, Pilar realized that she belonged to New York, her artistic soul too. If she would stay with Celia, Pilar's artistic spirit would slowly die day by day, just as Pilar herself would die ... The revolution / politics somehow "determined" Pilar's citizenship, and from this point we can say that "*citizenship becomes equivalent to life itself*"¹³. Pilar's life was in New York and not in Cuba.

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¹² Popescu, Veronica. pp.161.

¹³ Mitchell, David T. "National Families and Familial Nations: Communista Americans in Cristina Garcia's *Dreaming in Cuban*." *Tulsa Studies in Women's Literature*, vol. 15, no. 1, 1996, pp. 54. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/463972. Accessed 18 June 2021.

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